

SOCIOECONOMIC ALTERNATIVES AND LOCAL DEVELOPMENT: BANANA PRATA IN THE SERRA REGION OF THE MUNICIPALITY OF ITAGUAÍ AND SURROUNDINGS¹

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Abstract

This article has the character of a theoretical essay and seeks to promote the debate on the socioeconomic possibilities of bananas and their by-products in the rural territory of the mountain region of the municipality of Itaguaí and its surroundings (Rio de Janeiro - Brazil). Taking as reference the historical-cultural potential and fertile particularities of the biome and unique subclimate of the space, as well as its pre-disposition for the promotion of a local productive arrangement – APL and a Geographical Indication – GI (Indication of Origin - IP). For the development of this article, a combination of documentary research and bibliographical bases was used as a methodology, associated with participant observation using an ethnographic method, carried out in the 2020-2021 biennium, with a review carried out in the second half of 2022. Finally, this essay presents a narrative about the productive process of the silver banana and its by-products in the territory, based on the proposition of an endogenous development as a mechanism that propels economic autonomy and resistance of these rural communities, activities that have in the consanguineous, generational and knowledge aspects to do, elements that uniquely shape the process. Finally, this essay deals with difficulties and possibilities of instruments in the productive flow of silver banana and its by-products in the region, its main bottlenecks and its main potentialities. With the participation of local civil society, participatory and self-management instances, an instrument for the construction, execution and reconstruction of these long-term practices.

Keywords: Itaguaí - Rio de Janeiro – Brazil; silver banana; rural territory; local productive arrangement; geographical indication.

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1. Introduction

This article is an academic essay on the rural territory of the mountain region of the municipality of Itaguaí and its surroundings, a space that is limited between the neighborhoods of Mazomba, Santa Cândida, Raíz da Serra, Coroa Grande and the district of Ibituporanga, located in the municipality of Itaguaí (ITAGUAÍ, 2014), as well as regions of its fringes spatially composed of locations in the northeast of the municipality of Seropédica, northwest of the municipality of Piraí, west of the municipality of Rio Claro and southwest of the municipality of Mangaratiba. It is not possible to be borderline accurate because it is a mountainous region, difficult to access and with a predominance of dense rainforest, but which present among themselves a potential for human immaterialities, based on the process of valuing their symbolic, historical, cultural, socioeconomic and productive, biotic and power compositions (HAESBAERT, 2012)

The region has a low census, with its landscape predominantly composed of farms, lots, pastures, crops, small ranches, areas of extensive plantations and family farming, in addition to extensions of the Atlantic Forest and pastures. With misshapen houses, common in rural Brazilian locations, and occupational centers with low recency (IBGE, 1996). Based on Law No. 3,433 of May 17, 2016, and on the zoning map of the municipality of Itaguaí (ITAGUAÍ, 2016), the region is predominantly established as a Permanent Preservation Zone - ZPP, with a small central strip from northwest to southwest as Rural Residential Zone - ZRR, and one end at the center-east, determined as Residential Urban Expansion Zone - ZR-5, in addition to a line that cuts across the territory in a northwest-south direction, established as Services Zone - ZS (street from the Metropolitan Arch Highway).

The central focus of this article, with the character of a theoretical essay, is to deal with the socio-productive potential of silver bananas throughout the region, mainly in highlighting instances where the possibility of implementing a Local Productive Arrangement - APL and the Promotion of a Geographical Indication – GI (Indication of Origin - IP).

The silver banana is a product that historically forms part of the local production chain, a central instrument in the composition of the fertile particularities of handling and biotic peculiarities of the soil and the local climate. Production that occurs especially on the inclined plane, due to the protuberant relief and higher region (on average 150m above sea level) which favors a lower local temperature than in other urban locations (average of 28°C), having its climate is classified as AW (rainy summer with dry winter) (KOPPEN, 1938), and a relative humidity of 75% in annual average. Favorable conditions for banana production, due to tissue

hydration, inflorescence and uniformity of fruit color, significant vegetation cover, organic matter and soil classified as arginosoil (EMBRAPA, 2018).

Therefore, we seek to discuss the productive potential, advent of the silver banana produced in the mountain region of the municipality of Itaguaí and its surroundings, as an instrument that favors a unique production chain and with transformative potential for the territory and its local actors.

1.1 Methodology

The methodology used was the conjunction of a documentary research of bibliographic and telematic bases, in association with a participant observation, as an ethnographic method (VIEIRA; VIEIRA, 2018), carried out during the years 2020 and 2021, as an integral part of the doctoral research (by the author of this article), revised during the second half of 2022, while he participates as a member of the Council of Sustainable Agriculture and Fisheries of the Municipality of Itaguaí – COMASPI. These combined practices offer sources and contents, as well as provide new data, which end up jointly composing the same process of assimilation of information and absorption of phenomena, interpreted as perception of cultural aspects, natural phenomena and empirical knowledge, fundamental to the understanding of the ancestry of the community in question. (CANANÉA, 2013).

This research seeks to support its analysis from a particular understanding of what a territory is, understood here as a living space in a constant process of transformation, provided by the practice of its local actors who influence and are influenced by the environment and by specific characteristics of the environment. own space, such as: environmental, cultural, identity, social, economic, biotic aspects, among others. The sum of these characteristics constitutes a social texture linked to social and power relations, resulting in a sense of belonging, rich in particular symbolism.

The representation [...] is, therefore, a set defined in relation to the objectives of an actor. It is not, therefore, the “space”, but an environment constructed by the author, which communicates his intentions and the material reality through a semic system. Therefore, the place represented is no longer space, but its image, or rather, the territory seen and/or lived. It is, in short, the space that has become the territory of an actor, as long as it is taken in a social communication relationship. (RAFFESTIN, 1993 , p. 147).

Therefore, to understand the methodologies applied here with the concept of territories is to seek an interpretation based on the relationship between the researcher-observer and the studied object in its natural space. Action that builds a particular scientific analysis of that

environment, in that particular space-time (LÉVI-STRAUSS, 2005) so that this new analysis brings together “subject and object and can integrate with each other” (MORIN, 2007, p. 47 and 48), resulting in data and information that oppose and/or complement each other, directly or indirectly, and even change over time.

2. SILVER BANANA CULTURE IN THE REGION OF SERRA DE ITAGUAÍ AND SURROUNDINGS, ENDOGENOUS DEVELOPMENT AND ITS POTENTIAL.

It is worth highlighting the potential of in natura silver bananas, an action that dialogues with the practice of the universe of ethnoknowledge in which the predominance of “history and culture with deep roots that are passed from generation to generation” is observed (MPP, 2011 , p 4), established beyond just the professional context, which highlights “a way of life where work is free and has an autonomous and collective regime. It has a direct relationship with nature, with spirituality and mystique that raises respect and care” (IBID, 2011, p. 04).

These practices show generational predominance, characterized by blood ties and affection between the entities involved, an execution that approaches an ecology of knowledge as these actors promote a unique know-how, a native science, not applicable in other biotic, social conditions and cultural (SANTOS, 2007).

Where their activities are carried out in a traditional way, with low mechanization, with predominant organic fertilization and conventional crops, as well as having their work relationships directly related to the land and collective activities (ABRAMOVAY, 2010), where the use of draft animals, mainly in the loading of banana cultivation, made by horses or mules, carried out by parents, children and grandchildren of producers, mainly in properties farther from urban centers, or that have their banana plantations on an inclined plane (uphill).

Figure 01: Banana production on an inclined plane (top left), accumulation of silver bananas on rural roads in the region (bottom left), displacement of the banana production chain carried out by draft animals (right)
Source: top left BIRTH (2021), other COPAFIT images (2021)

Bearing in mind this multifunctional perspective, typical of Brazilian rural communities (BONNAL; MALUF, 2007), there is the potential for promoting a dynamic of a Local Productive Arrangement – APL of silver bananas from the Serra de Itaguaí region and surroundings. The formation of local productive arrangements is often determined by their links with identity territories. The productive specialization associated with a given territory is almost always the result of historical trajectories of construction of identities and formation of territorial ties (regional and local). “From a common social, cultural, political and economic base. [...] more conducive to being developed in environments favorable to interaction, cooperation and trust between actors”. (HASTENREITER, 2014 , p. 18).

Currently, banana producers in the region are looking for the possibility of implementing the APL of the silver banana in association with a collective mark as a Geographical Indication - GI (Indication of Origin - IP / banana from Itaguaí). IP is characterized by being the “ geographical name of a country, city, region or a locality of its territory that has become known as a center of production, manufacture or extraction of a certain product or provision of a certain service” (INPI, 2020 , s /P). This joint action aims to “identify and distinguish products or services from members of a legal entity [...] it is to indicate to the consumer that that product or service comes from members of a given entity (IBID, 2020, s/p).

In this specific case, managed by farmers in the region, institutionalized by the Cooperativa de Agricultores Familiares de Itaguaí - COOPAFIT, a regulated collective entity that has been operating since November 19, 1015, in the management, collaboration, promotion

and development of local rural activity (COOPAFIT, 2015). Action that has been counting on technical-institutional support from the Secretariat of Agriculture and Fisheries of the City Hall of Itaguaí - SMAP. Process that to date (December 2022) is in the last stage of analysis, with the National Institute of Intellectual Property - INPI, the highest body responsible for the assignment of the geographical indication - GI in Brazil.

The possibility of developing a silver banana APL, in line with an IP in the territory, expresses a degree of organization of local actors, as it “ identifies the origin of products or services when the location has become known or when determined characteristic or quality of the product or service is due to its origin” (INPI, 2017), providing a perception as a larger encompassing part of the same reference territory in the practice not only of products (banana), but also in possible services such as tourism, hotel and culinary sectors, which may occur as an unfolding of this current movement, building other wide and varied possibilities in the place, without losing its instances of conservation, as well as the capital increase of these services as a value-added product.

The definitive revelation of each territory will only occur when its population, through social actors, recognizes its characterizing elements of social and territorial cohesion , during, or shortly after, the process of building identity and proposing its vision of the future. (MDA, 2005 , p. 29)

These practices currently in motion in the territory, present a scenario of particular socioeconomic potential “encouragement of territorialization and collective and non-sectoral development” (ZIMMERMANN; GRISA; TECCIO ; et al. 2014. P. 546). As a “tool capable of helping a community to promote its position in the market, create its reputation and protect it from unfair competition, in addition to better organizing collective economic activity” (REGALADO , et al, 2012, p. 06), add value to the product, as well as encouraging production on a larger scale, increasing economic efficiency and local social equity.

The action that generates the potential of both the Local Productive Arrangement and the Indication of Origin of the silver banana from the mountain region of the municipality of Itaguaí and its surroundings, is largely supported by the process of sociocultural strengthening of the farmers who live in the area , which for centuries develop a significant variety of by-products from the silver banana, where it was possible to observe the production of a significant variety of bananas, raisins, dehydrated, in syrups, canned. In addition to other foods that have the banana fruit as their central element, such as green banana biomass, green banana flour, cakes and ice cream, among others.

Figure 02: Silver banana in natura, with origin indication seal (center) and variety of by-products of silver banana (left and right)

Source: COOPAFIT (2021)

The use of these banana by-products, in partnership with the fruit itself in natura, socioeconomically stimulates a significant slice of male and female farmers to promote the added value of their inventions, as well as helping to enter niche markets, hitherto considered inaccessible to these producers. What they see in APL's and IP's proposal for the silver banana as a valuation process from the inside (the territory) to the outside, due to the fact that the product does not just have a good appearance, but rather a business differentiation.

It is of fundamental importance to mention that the process of conditioning an APL and an IP of silver banana in the region, are not limited to dealing with the restricted market system, but mainly as an element of rescuing the traditionalities of the rural producers in the region, from the activity of organic banana farming that directly needs the particular sociocultural traits of the place, while multi-scalar processes that are symbolically developed from the participation of the actors of the territory, and that promote their practices due to their relationship with their space, build and rebuild these symbolisms and consequently their relations of belonging. (FERNANDES, 2009).

For this, the execution of a local endogenous development must be understood and stimulated as a practice and territorial socioeconomic increment from the direct participation of its local actors, aiming at the collective well-being, the conservation of the environment and the valorization of the local productive arrangements . From this perspective, the endogenous development of the territory of Serra de Itaguaí and surroundings must “consist of endogenizing a series of previously exogenous variables (such as human capital, the environment, etc.)” (ARAÚJO, 2014, p. 02) , based on valuing the collective and self-management practices.

The term self-management is related to the search for alternative and collective ways of producing and organizing work. [...] refers to the search and configuration of fair and democratic organizational processes or modes, where members of a collective organization (solidarity economy enterprises, for example) are engaged in decision-making processes, activities and controls organizational. In these types of organizations, the ends are always social, even if the means are economic [...] a way of managing collective organizations that seeks to eliminate hierarchies, ownership and control of means and knowledge related to management and production. Self-management has a multidimensional character: social, political, economic and technical. It marks the distance from subordination relationships and points to democracy and direct participation of those involved (RIGO, 2014 , p. 21 and 22)

The socioeconomic promotion of space, from a self-managed perspective, aims at broad development, considering a bottom-up ideal (*Buttomup*) It is contrary to the exclusionary marketing logic, since this proposal must be built essentially from the available resources (biome), local potential and environmental respect, horizontal distribution of the workforce, and promotion of innate knowledge and the local models available for articulating the production and consumption, understood as important factors for the promotion of the local economy.

One can observe as challenges the need to expand collective work strategies based on the expertise of these local actors, mainly family farmers, COOPAFIT, other associations, councils, interested public entities, SMAP, micro-entrepreneurs in the region, teaching, research and extension institutions, between others. A fabric that still presents weaknesses and discontinuities not only in the construction of dialogue, but also in the very execution of territorial public policies.

Another point observed as of fundamental importance (for the success of the proposal indicated here) is the appreciation of tacit knowledge (knowledge acquired and passed on through interaction, non-codified knowledge), transmitted generationally between local actors, connected with governance and other instances of direct action of the local civil society, articulated around a common interest (VILLELA, PINTO, 2009), commonly structured in a participatory dialogic practice.

Therefore, both the proposal of the APL and the IP of Banana Prata in the territory, walk together as a logic of social management. As “social management is configured as a process of building the emancipation of human beings. Emancipation understood as getting rid of someone's tutelage and seeking autonomy.” (CANÇADO et al, 2013, p.19). Be they socio-cultural representation and identity (ethno-knowledge), preservation of the local biome, socio-historical and consanguine rescue of its actors and socio-economic autonomy vis-à-vis foreign markets.

Aiming at a joint and participatory construction (demands and potentialities) of a democratic, autonomous and horizontal practice among its members, actions that have proven to improve competitive performance, adaptation to adversity, leadership, spatial understanding of the territory, among others. A body of foundational practices that replace typically hierarchical tools in exchange for multiscalar development and the promotion of future social skills.

There is also a need to articulate productive flow processes, considering that currently, a significant part of these products and by-products are sold in small local fairs and some produce in the region. And as a last resort, resold to middlemen who resell to markets in other locations in the west zone and Baixada Fluminense, or to the Central de Abastecimento of the state of Rio de Janeiro - CEASA. Therefore, there is no point in having a single productive capacity and participatory action by the members involved, if the commercialization process for this product and by-product does not find an effective market channel for its expansion.

Figure 03: Commercialization of silver banana and its by-products in the urban center of the territory
Source: own.

Despite the observed difficulties mentioned above, it is possible to state that there is a productive potential for silver banana in the territory and that it presents a substantial predisposition for its expansion, with unique socioeconomic potential for the local actors involved and that favors the rescue of local traditions. Stimuli that in the medium/long term can definitely promote the autonomy of the agents involved in a way that associates the social dimension itself to a daily dynamic that is so unique, impossible to be replicated in other natural or synthetic environments.

Which has in its socioeconomic and historical-cultural apparatuses particular significance both in terms of “understanding of knowledge and techniques developed by humans in relation to the environment in different cultures” (CAMPOS, 2002, p. 10), as an empirical science of these local actors, who, by producing a variety of products and by-products, re-signify not only the local production chain, but also provide the emergence of new alternatives for maintenance and resistance of their own places of origin.

3. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that there is already a trial of Local Productive Arrangement - APL of silver banana in the mountain region of the municipality of Itaguaí and its surroundings, although this action is being carried out in an almost intrinsic way and not previously planned by its local actors, in addition to this factor is the imminent implementation of an Indication of Origin -IP in the territory, a combination of practices that in the medium/long term can collectively provide joint alternatives that favor endogenous development, based on the appreciation of producers places and practices of ethnoknowledge.

The current socioeconomic practices in progress in the territory stimulate the development of alternatives with the final intention of territorialization (or reterritorialization), so that the biotic and sociocultural disposition of the space itself is the main driver and supplier of its activities, becoming a mechanism of suggestion that balance the external forced processes (Most times globalizing economic and/or political), providing for the local actors endogenous development mechanisms, concerning good practices of common good.

Although the presence of the Municipal Secretariat of Agriculture and Fisheries of Itaguaí - SMAP is observable, it is worth mentioning the lack of participatory public-private institutions that are installed in the region, which sometimes act sporadically and consequently incipient with the demand indicated by these rural actors, factors that have become aggravating

in recent years due to the decrease in public investments at the federal level carried out after the obtuse cuts occurred in the Temer-Bolsonaro governments.

However, it is worth highlighting the advancement of these good socioeconomic practices by these actors, especially after the peak period of the pandemic in Brazil (2020-2021), which indicates in the medium / long term the expansion of socio-productive activities of silver banana in the region and of its by-products, as a chain development of family farmers, traders, associations, cooperatives, inns, tourist locations, members aggregated under the sign in a way to foster a proposal for collective and aggregating increment, which can be endorsed by an APL and an IP , constituting a unique identity of the product.

Finally, the proposal for endogenous developments, tested here based on an APL and IP sign, has as its main purpose to stimulate and encourage the promotion and autonomy of local actors insofar as “they are encouraged to build, select, develop and carry out the social control of collective projects that meet the productive, economic, cultural, environmental and social demands of the territories” (ZIMMERMANN; GRISA; TECCIO; et al. 2014, p.546).

It is even essential to point out that the participation of local rural communities, their listening and approval, is the main pillar of support for the activities proposed here, and that their promotions take place in a self-managed movement that values local endogenous development, with a greater incidence and support for public policies from different spheres, even though the decision-making core ultimately belongs to local rural actors.

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